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**Sustainable and Green Electronics for Circular
Economy (SUSTRONICS)**

PROCESS DESCRIPTION

METHODOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE
MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF WEARABLE
SYSTEMS

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Abstract

In this work we describe the issues and environmental impact of the current state-of-art methods for manufacturing of smart wearable systems/smart clothing and propose a new methodology for an improved process of wearable system manufacturing, describe this process, provide guidelines for implementing this process, and analyze and discuss the environmental and sustainability improvements this improved methodology can provide.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Smart wearable systems or smart clothing hold significant potential to enhance our lives considerably. However, numerous unresolved challenges hinder the development of innovative applications for this technology and limit the broader market adoption of products based on it. Unfortunately, the current state-of-the-art manufacturing process of smart clothing is inefficient and wasteful both in physical resources used as well as time and energy used for the process and logistics involved. In this document we describe a proposed new methodology for a more sustainable manufacturing process of wearable systems, which would reduce the ecological footprint of each smart clothing item produced while at the same time making the manufacturing of smart clothing more economically viable.

1.1 Motivation

Wearable devices such as sensors and actuators, which can be attached to the human body, facilitate the collection of data related to the body or the surrounding environment. This capability enables a range of valuable applications in fields including medicine [1][2][3], rehabilitation [4][5][6], human-machine interaction [7][8][9], safety [10][11][12], sports [13][14][15], safe and graceful aging [16] [17][18], healthy living [19][20][21], performance measurement [22] [23][24], regaining lost body functionality [25][26][27], entertainment [28][29][30], and even gaining new abilities such as additional senses [31][32][33], enhanced physical capabilities [34][35][36] or improved learning [37][38][39].

Wearable devices vary in complexity from the most basic, typically standalone, devices, that are equipped with sensors, feedback mechanisms [40], power source [41][42] and usually wireless connectivity [43] and are worn somewhere on the body. These standalone devices are exemplified by smartwatches and sports/activity trackers. They are self-contained and localized devices, and thus are usually sufficient for more simple and generic use-cases, while not precise enough for more complex ones, as they might lack sufficient number of sensor locations and types of sensors [44].

Incorporating multiple wearable devices on the body necessitates a form of

networking to leverage numerous advantages. These benefits include enhanced data reliability through multiple sensor fusion [45][46], a greater variety of data modalities (such as inertial, EEG, and EMG) from different places on the body [47][48], as well as more complex data that includes several parts of the body for uses such as motion capture [49][50], location-based feedback [51][52] and distributed wearable computing [53][54]. Achieving these benefits typically requires a standardized networking protocol among the potentially heterogeneous devices on the human body.

Unfortunately, the existing approaches to applying multiple networked smart devices on human body are currently not only highly impractical, but also attempts at mass producing related solutions such as smart clothing are complex, require a lot of energy, materials and other resources, and thus have a high impact on the environment. Due to the complexity of this problem field, in the next section we will introduce the background information of this problem in more detail, followed by a description of the best current state-of-art solutions to these problems and analysis of their environmental impact.

We believe, that solving these problems in the smart wearable manufacturing will have significant impact on the sustainability of this class of products and thus also will make the wide range of benefits of smart wearables more available to the general public. Due to this, in the next chapter we will describe a proposed solution - improved methodology for manufacturing of smart wearables, provide guidelines for implementing this improved process, and discuss the improved sustainability aspects of this process.

1.2 Background and problem definition

When talking about multiple networked wearable devices, there are several common terms that are usually used:

- Body Area Networks (BAN) [55],
- Wireless Body Area Networks (WBAN)[56],
- Body Sensor Networks (BSN) [57] or
- Medical Body Area Networks (MBAN) [58].

In this report the term BAN will be used to describe all of the categories mentioned above as they are a subset of BAN. Historically before BANs there was also a related concept called the Personal Area Network (PAN) which was designed specifically for data sharing between personal electronic devices [59]. The difference was, that PAN does not look at such aspects as information exchange between components and devices, support for multiple physical links, interfacing with other networks or shorter communication ranges, and also does not emphasize smart clothing or wearable applications [60].

The IEEE standard 802.15.6 [61] standardize the Wireless Body Area Networks (BANs). Although this standard does not encompass wired BANs,

it does cover communication where the medium is human body itself, employing technologies such as Body Coupled Communication (BCC) [62].

When BANs are integrated into garments, the result is called Smart clothing [63]. Some experts posit that smart clothing represents the next evolution of BANs, offering inherent advantages over previous approaches [64]. The primary benefit of smart clothing lies in its personal, comfortable nature, being worn close to the body and used almost universally [65]. Consequently, smart features can be incorporated without causing any inconvenience to the user, who only needs to wear the clothing itself, eliminating the need for additional sensor devices that would be worn separately.

The smart clothing can be split into three levels [66]:

- passive smart clothing, that can sense the environment only,
- active smart clothing, which can both sense and react to the environment and
- very smart clothing, that is smart clothing with the additional capability to adapt its behavior to the current circumstances.

Since smart clothing should be as easy to maintain and use as ordinary textiles, it is critical for them to be well integrated with textiles [67] and to have compatibility with established manufacturing processes for conventional clothing items, such as sewing, knitting or printing [68].

Textiles that incorporate electronic components (e.g., sensors, actuators, wires, or batteries essential for smart clothing) are commonly referred to as smart textiles [69][70], e-textiles [71] or smart fabrics [72]. Given that some literature also uses the term "smart textiles" for materials with smart properties [73] but without electronic components, we will use the term "e-textiles" in this document for clarity.

E-textiles are frequently designed to facilitate the transmission of data, and in some instances, power between wearable devices. Consequently, they necessitate the integration of conductive pathways. Therefore, e-textiles can be entirely conductive [74][75][76], comprise conductive fibers [77][78][79] or yarns [80][81][82], have several conductive layers [83][84][85], have the conductive material be laminated on [86][74][87] or printed [88][89][90] or have integrated appropriately elastic separate wires [91][92][93] or cables [94][95][96].

There are also multiple physical properties that might be critical for e-textile based smart clothing, such as elasticity [97][98] [99], washability [100][101][102] or stretchability [103][104][105], so that they function just as regular clothing enabling more users to gather real-time data while being comfortable due to the unobtrusive nature [106] of their smart clothing. Sometimes the clothing can even improve the comfort of the wearer above that of regular clothing [107].

There are multiple key issues plaguing the promising technology of smart clothing, that prevent it from reaching its full potential. Smart clothing is a highly interdisciplinary field [108] and includes such research fields as clothing manufacturing [109], design [110], material science [111], wearable energy sources [112], low-power communication [113], embedded electronics [114], sensor

networks [115], embedded algorithms and embedded signal processing [116] and many others. Thus to advance the state of the art in smart clothing, researchers and experts across various disciplines have had to collaborate to establish a common language and to define critical issues for moving forward. The most recent example of such collaboration is 41 prominent contributors coming together to release a book ¹ that was reissued and updated in 2022 [117]. This book represents the current understanding of the field and its key challenges.

A key challenge/opportunity for smart clothing has been proposed to be - *”Using wearable technology should not require effort but be logical, immediate and intuitive - even taken for granted. Technology should not need to be installed or have manuals - energy sources being held within the garment’s fabric. And the entire garment should be machine-washable with electronic components encapsulated.”* [117].

This means, that current impracticality of the smart clothing is holding it back from wider real world use. The main contributing factors are washability, robustness to wear and tear and manufacturability. This opinion is echoed by other researchers, such as [67][118]. Our own work in this project and beyond has also led us to the same conclusions [119][8][120][121][122].

A smart clothing system in addition to the clothing aspect itself consists of five groups of smart components [123]:

1. **Interfaces** - external information exchange endpoints for the smart clothing - meant for communication with the environment, external devices or the wearer themselves. These include actuators [124], sensors [125] and external links for communication [126], that connect the smart clothing to the external world (for example WiFi [127] or Bluetooth [128]);
2. **Communication components** - internal information exchange or interconnect in the smart clothing itself [129], which provides links for information and energy transfer internally among the smart clothing components. Some examples of these include wires [130], wireless connections [131] and intra-body communication [132];
3. **Data management components** - parts of the smart clothing that are responsible for data storage (memory) and data processing (computing). Some examples of these include signal processing circuits [133], microprocessors (MCU) [134], RAM [135], special purpose processors [136], ROM [137], SD Cards [138] and flash memory [139];
4. **Energy management components** - systems in smart clothing that are responsible for powering it (providing, storing and gathering the required energy). Some examples of these power sources include batteries [140], capacitors [141], energy harvesting solutions [142] and wireless charging [143];

¹The authors come from well established manufacturers and research institutions working on smart clothing in such countries as United States, United Kingdom, Germany, Finland, Netherlands, China, Northern Ireland, Switzerland and Denmark.

5. **Integrated circuits** - electronic circuits built into the smart clothing in order to provide the required functionality by connecting passive electronic components [144], integrated circuits [145] and other embedded parts.

The interfaces themselves have challenges that are mainly the same for regular wearable devices such as smartwatches and are not unique to smart clothing specifically. They are also rapidly changing and evolving. Due to the fact, that all sensors and actuators could have differing location requirements on the wearers body [146][147] one key problem can be defined as **solving the ability to connect these interfaces anywhere on the smart clothing** for all of different use-cases. External communication links are usually wireless, and can be very specific to the selected application. The fact that these links are wireless can introduce security and privacy risks and vulnerabilities [148], which can be somewhat mitigated by relying on well known and established standards like WiFi or Bluetooth [149].

Communication components are usually wireless. This can lead to multiple problems:

1. Each component requires power. If it is impossible or unfeasible to deliver the power, then each of these components require a separate power source/battery, which needs to be handled and charged separately [150]. On the other hand, wireless power delivery is inefficient [151] and has two critical limitations in wearable applications: (1) it is blocked by human body [152]; (2) maximum power near human body is limited due to health concerns. [153];
2. Maximum number of components in wearable systems close to each other is practically limited by interference between multiple wireless transmitters [154][155]. Additionally, the available frequency bands limit this even further [156];
3. Due to very limited computing power of embedded components, the security and privacy is also limited. The reasons include such examples as: (a) weak cryptography due to limited resources [157], (b) high risks of highly impactful data leaks and/or malicious interference [158] caused by the intimate closeness and access of the wearable system to the private behavioral and medical data of the user [159] that could be protected by regulations such as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation, European Union)². Research shows, that this is especially critical due to existence of data brokers selling personal health information gathered from apps and wearable systems, including real time data on activities, location and behavior [160]. Additionally smart wearable systems usually have some health related goals, and thus can be subject to even stricter regulations [161].

Due to the above mentioned privacy issues, there is currently high interest in more private communication technologies, so that the private information is

²European Parliament Directive 95/46/EC

not broadcast as widely. One such new and promising technology currently under development is communication through human body and skin [162]. Unfortunately it is still not available for general use. This technology also is not capable of delivering sufficient power through human body, as the maximum safe power limits would then be exceeded [153]. Another option that solves all of these issues is using wires for connections. Unfortunately wires introduce a new problem in the context of wearable systems - they break easily if mishandled [163]. There are attempts at solving this by using flexible wire technologies, but many of them can still degrade rapidly due to loss of infused conductive particles while the garment is used or washed [164]. There is an ongoing research effort to solve these problems of wires, but still no standard or consensus exists on how the wires can be practically used for communications in the smart clothing in an integral fashion [68]. Thus another **key problem with smart clothing is the lack of practical, robust and manufacturable power and data interconnect for use in smart clothing.**

Data management components are embedded components, that are usually well standardized and the only relevant problems that they have in relation to smart clothing are thus also relevant to integrated circuits as discussed below.

Energy management components have two problems related to smart clothing: (1) power delivery is needed to all components that require it as already discussed in section for communication components; (2) smart clothing potentially can have a lot of electronic components - these might require power delivery at the same time while relatively far away from each other, which means that power delivery components/circuit must have low time constant, appropriate resistance and maximum power delivery [165], especially at the time of boot-up, as sensors or actuators when turned on at once, usually have high power draw, resulting in sub-optimal or delayed power or signal edges, that can lead to a number of problems. This means that another **key problem is reliable and rapid delivery of power at all points in the smart clothing in a sufficient way.**

Integrated circuits (and all other electronic components) in the smart clothing need to be protected from such things as environment, moisture during washing, body moisture during use and other damaging or corrosive substances the clothing might come into contact with [101]. For non-clothing related circuits, electronic components can be encased in epoxy or similar materials [166]. The need for flexibility in smart clothing means, that such inflexible/hard insulation materials cannot be used at least in some places in smart clothing. They also add additional strain to the joint between the inflexible material and a flexible component, which accelerates wear and tear. Some research into flexible components has been done, but they need to be enclosed in insulation of matching flexibility both to the component and the surrounding fabric [167]. The insulating/protective material has to be created in such a way that it takes on strain or damage before the component it protects needs to, thus also acting as a strain relief. Also all joints between wires and components have to be water tight, as even microscopic openings can lead to water ingress through capillary action [168]. These protection and strain relief solutions are re-engineered and

designed from ground up each time a new smart clothing product is being developed - this has both environmental and sustainability implications, as well as implications of higher costs, longer development times and potentially sub-optimal solutions [169]. This is especially true due to existence of multiple complex failure modes in washing that must be countered [100]. For long term adaption it is important for smart clothing to be easy to maintain and wash, just as ordinary textiles [67]. Thus for useability another **key problem is the absence of appropriate and manufacturable universal solution for protection of electronic components from moisture and environmental effects in the smart clothing.**

The above mentioned problems combined with the general complexity of smart clothing manufacturability, the complex interactions between multiple industries involved in the smart clothing (e.g. electronics and textile), missing integrated testing, manufacturing and qualification standards lead to an industry gap, that usually forces developers and manufacturers to start from scratch when developing a new wearable product, and due to the fact that new unique processes are not easily automated, lots of manual, expensive and slow processes lead to inefficiencies, unreliable products and general waste, which is not sustainable in the long term [170][68].

This leads to the **main problem for widespread adoption and exploitation of economies of scale in smart clothing manufacturing, which could reduce the environmental impact of manufacturing per unit is the complex, largely manual, non-standardized and interwoven smart clothing manufacturing process.**

1.3 Current state-of-the-art

Current state-of-the-art clothing manufacturing process [171] consists of the following steps:

1. **Planning** (pre-manufacturing) steps encompass the design of the clothing, the development of the design into a viable product concept, and the meticulous planning of the production process;
2. **Fabric selection and sourcing** - involve choosing suitable fabrics and manufacturers that meet product requirements and supply chain demands. This step also includes conducting fabric quality inspections before proceeding to subsequent manufacturing stages;
3. **Garment accessory, trim and closure selection and sourcing** - involves choosing suitable materials and their manufacturers, akin to the fabric selection process. This step also requires implementing stringent quality control measures for these materials before they are used in the production process;
4. **Garment sizing and fit** - involve determining specific sizing standards or customizing sizes for each customer. These decisions, along with considerations for fit, guide the actual pattern development of the clothing;

5. **Pattern construction** - involves designing two-dimensional shapes that will be cut from the fabric and then assembled into the final garment;
6. **Fabric spreading and cutting** - involve initially spreading and transporting the fabric using specialized machinery. Subsequently, software is utilized to optimize the material usage by determining the optimal locations for cutting, thereby minimizing waste. The patterns are then cut from the fabric using computer-controlled cutting devices such as knives, lasers, or water jets. Following this, the cuts undergo quality control, where any defective components are re-cut. Finally, all components are marked, sorted, and bundled for further processing;
7. **Fabric-joining** - involves assembling the cut pieces into a garment using methods such as sewing, stitching, adhesive bonding, or thermal welding. The choice of joining technology is determined by the garment's intended purpose and the required physical properties, including elasticity, damage resistance, and water permeability;
8. **Garment finishing** - involves the application of custom designs to the garment, as well as chemical and mechanical processing;
9. **Quality control and quality assurance** - involve evaluating the final products' quality and implementing potential quality improvements throughout the manufacturing process;
10. **Final touches** - include attaching care labels with standardized care instructions, folding and ironing the garment, and packaging it appropriately for distribution and sales.

All of these manufacturing steps for clothing are well established. There is a long list of existing clothing manufacturing standards, that these steps must comply with. These include:

- general fair trade standards like *Fair Trade Certified*³ or *SA8000*⁴;
- quality of materials and safety of manufacturing process standards like *ECO PASSPORT*⁵ or *ISO 9001:2015*⁶
- production management and financing standards like *WRAP*⁷;
- textile quality standards like *OCS*⁸, *GOTS*⁹ or *RWS*¹⁰;

³Fair Trade USA, <https://www.fairtradecertified.org/>

⁴Social Accountability International, <https://sa-intl.org/resources/sa8000-getting-started/>

⁵OEKO-TEX 100 independent test and certification system for confidence in textiles, <https://www.oeko-tex.com/en/our-standards/oeko-tex-standard-100>

⁶ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems, <https://www.iso.org/standard/62085.html>

⁷Worldwide Responsible Apparel Production, <https://wrapcompliance.org/en/>

⁸Organic Content Standard, <https://textileexchange.org/organic-content-standard/>

⁹Global Organic Textile Standards, <https://global-standard.org/>

¹⁰Responsible Wool Standard, <https://textileexchange.org/responsible-wool-standard/>

- standards for specific related technologies, and sub-steps of these steps, such as *Regulation (EU) No 1007/2011*¹¹.

This list is not at all exhaustive and only illustrates the wide coverage of standardization related to the classic clothing manufacturing process in contrast with the smart clothing manufacturing process which is still in its infancy. Due to the fact that traditional "cut and sew" methods are not easily applicable [172] most smart wearable systems are built from scratch with little standardization in the manufacturing process. Recently, multiple organizations have been working on development of standards with which the ready smart clothing products should comply (which are relevant only after they are manufactured) - some examples of these include:

- European Committee for Standardization (CEN) technical committee CEN TC 248/WG 31;
- International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) technical committee IEC TC 124;
- ASTM International technical committee ASTM D13.50;
- International Organization for Standardization technical committee ISO/TC 38/WG 32;
- American Association of Textile Chemists & Colorists (AATCC) technical committee AATCC RA111.

As recently as 2021 there were **4 related terminology standards and 18 test standards** either already published or under development [173]. These include standards on durability, laundering resistance, electrical resistance, washability, thermal properties of e-textiles, conductive yarns and connectors and mechanical properties smart clothing.

Some calls for standardization of small parts of smart clothing manufacturing have been noteworthy recently, e.g. design and labeling standardization [174]. There have also been efforts to prioritize future standardization efforts for smart clothing [63]. Still, no standardized manufacturing process for smart clothing has been defined or adopted as of now. The reasons most likely include the wide range of requirements for current smart clothing developer, such as unique sensor and actuator placement needs and problems with their connections. This is complicated even further by existing competing interconnect technologies, that can be adapted from other fields for use in the smart clothing field, but each have a unique advantage and disadvantage profile depending on the specific application [175][176]. Thus, currently no universal smart clothing manufacturing standard has been feasible.

An interesting approach with a possibility to solve the problem with placement of many sensors and actuators in custom places of smart clothing is

¹¹Regulation (EU) No 1007/2011 of the European Parliament and the Council of 27 September 2011 on textile fibre names and related labelling and marking of the fibre composition of textile products

related to universal interconnects. Such approaches could allow decoupling of the development of interconnect technology from the smart clothing manufacturing process, which could enable the standardization of this process without previous knowledge of how the specific interconnect would be used in the final smart clothing garment in the future. There have been multiple explorations of this concept by researchers, such as:

- The *wearable motherboard* [177] is an idea, related to making the smart clothing into a "meta wearable" where sensors and actuators can be connected as needed. To make this approach possible, a grid of interconnect wires within the smart clothing was developed and these wires were connected by specialized routing electronics, that could route the data and power flow between the sensors and actuators in the smart clothing item [178].
- An even further evolution of the previous idea is a fabric with regularly interwoven copper wires. This fabric can then be cut or connected as needed in order to create a wearable circuit, that could even work without any active routing nodes [179]. Such interconnect fabric, if manufactured in bulk, could serve as the foundation for a universal standard for smart clothing manufacturing.

Such universal interconnect fabrics for smart clothing could potentially be manufacturing using a wide variety of technologies, such as (more are being developed as well):

- embroidery [180];
- transfer printing [181];
- 2D printing [182] such as ink-jet;
- 3D printing [183];
- weaving a fabric with conductive yarns/wires [184];
- metal-textile laser welding [185].

This interconnect fabric idea has been around for some time, and some attempts with CNC embroidery machines [186] have been quite interesting. Even *Google* has launched their own smart fabric manufacturing project called *Jacquard* [187]. Still to date there are still no serious manufacturing attempts to date of smart clothing based on universal interconnect fabric, which is not an early prototype. Thus the potential of standardization related benefits, that this could lead to, such as easier entry into the smart wearables market with less waste, universal adaptation of new, highly resilient and complex wearable interconnect technologies and less time and materials spent on manufacturing smart clothing items with unique and useful functionality [63] are still not realized. Even the promising *Google Jacquard* project has only resulted in custom fashion products of small production runs, such as *Levi's* jackets and

Saint Laurent backpacks which are not using universal interconnect fabric as a basis, and instead use the wires in the fabric as a custom wearable input device.

This means, that there is still a **current gap in smart clothing manufacturing process standardization**. We attempt to close this gap by defining specific standardization requirements in the next section and based on that we propose and outline steps for a new standardized smart clothing manufacturing process. This process will later be validated in simulations and its feasibility demonstrated in practical pilot experiments.

1.4 Environmental impact of current solutions

Because of the aforementioned and the fact that the smart clothing market is predicted to grow rapidly (and even predicted to exceed the mobile phone market) [188] it can be assumed to be the future of wearable sensing, capable of delivering a higher order of magnitude beneficial impact than previous wearable technologies. This instead means that with increased scale of production all wasteful aspects in manufacturing have much greater impact on sustainability, and any improvements in recycle-ability or longevity of the products as well as in the manufacturing process would have a great sustainability impact.

A big problem currently with the previously mentioned underdeveloped factors of smart clothing related to washability, manufacturability and robustness to wear and tear have serious sustainability/environmental implications due to the fact, that the less resistant to use and washing the manufactured item is, the shorter its effective life and the faster it turns into waste, thus increasing the environmental impact. Thus any improvements in these areas can significantly impact the sustainability of smart clothing manufacturing and use.

Existing state-of-art wireless BANs introduce two additional sustainability problems - (1) each wireless device or sensor requires its own batteries, meaning that more rare earth materials must be used for manufacturing more batteries and more resources are wasted on battery charging which is an inefficient process, especially in the case of wireless charging; (2) energy efficiency of wireless transmissions is usually worse than planned, due to the fact that other devices might be transmitting at the same time and place, thus leading to collisions and interference, which in turn leads to more power spent on the wireless transmissions in order to successfully send and receive them, especially in crowded areas. If wireless transmission can be replaced where possible with wired alternatives, less wasted energy would be used, thus increasing sustainability of the solution.

Finally, the highest current sustainability impact of smart clothing manufacturing is in the manufacturing process itself. Many different manufacturers are forced to reinvent the wheel and use unique non-standardized low-yield processes for each smart clothing item type. This means more material waste due to lack of scale and high amount of manufacturing failures due to unreliable and even manual processes. This also means, that during the manufacturing the smart clothing items might need to be shipped long

distances between different specialists (clothing, wiring, fashion, electronics, sensors, washability etc.) introducing environmental costs of this extra shipping. This can be solved by allowing for universal adaptation of complex and highly resilient wearable interconnect technologies as well as development of new even better ones, while allowing the manufacturers of smart clothing to spend less time, effort and materials in order to develop new smart clothing items with unique and useful functionality [63]. This problem is exacerbated even more by the fact that the existing clothing manufacturing industry is very large in the scale of investments and equipment deployed - on the trillion dollar scale (1.53 trillion USD in 2022[189]), thus each new type of manufacturing process for smart clothing necessitates a lot of replaced and adjusted equipment leading to even more waste.

Chapter 2

Proposed solution

In order to propose a solution we will first define requirements that this solution must cover, and then we will describe the actual proposed methodology, describe implementation guidelines of this methodology, and discuss the sustainability impacts of the proposed methodology. Then in the next chapter we will discuss practical validation of this proposed solution so that in the next phases of the project the process and its sustainability impact can be validated.

2.1 Requirements & Specification

For the smart clothing manufacturing process standardization to be successful, it has to have **maximum compatibility with the modern clothing manufacturing process** which is described above. The main reasons are:

- The clothing manufacturing process itself has been developed and refined for many centuries. Even in 1800's the clothing industry employed a large amount of people [190]. Also many modern innovations, such as computer programming, are traceable back to innovations in clothing manufacturing, for example automated jacquard looms [191].
- The clothing manufacturing industry currently is huge - it has been called the 7th largest economy as compared to countries by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) value [192] and existing investments and deployed equipment are on the trillion dollar scale (1.53 trillion USD in 2022[189]). This means that the more deviations are introduced from the modern clothing manufacturing process, the more waste and need for additional investments will arise worldwide.

It is obvious, that for a manufacturing standard to be globally adapted it **must be economically viable**. The more of existing manufacturing processes, infrastructure and workforce can be re-used, the more likely it is that the smart clothing manufacturing process will succeed. Also for a breakthrough innovation to emerge usually recombinant search and selection is required instead of completely new ideas [193].

Sustainability is a key consideration in this project. It is easy to see, that if the new process will force existing equipment to be replaced, this will have a major sustainability impact, due to the existing scale of clothing manufacturing industry. While other approaches, such as circular economy and recycling [174] are being explored for reduction of the environmental effect of smart textile manufacturing, the process improvements themselves are of great impact in this area [194]. If these innovations are implemented carefully, even growing textile and clothing manufacturing industry, can result in reduced carbon-dioxide emissions[195]. A sustainable smart clothing supply chain must be built on a closed - from material acquisition to recycling [196]. The classic clothing industry has been slowly moving towards these goals for a long time, and reuse of parts of these supply chains will also reuse these sizable sustainability investments.

As a result, **clear interfaces with the existing modern clothing manufacturing processes must be established re-using as much as possible of existing processes, knowledge base and equipment.**

Some efforts for standardization of smart textile manufacturing go back as far as 2003 - even then it was emphasized, that compatibility with the standard clothing manufacturing processes and machinery is critical [172]. Some more recent attempts even show examples of production process standardization of electronic textiles [186]. Unfortunately there is still no discussion of interconnect configuration standardization, which could provide benefits not only in the smart textile manufacturing process but also later down the line in the smart clothing manufacturing process.

The fact, that many possible integration types exist between the smart clothing and embedded electronics [197] together with the existence of the previously mentioned efforts to isolate the smart textile manufacturing from the clothing manufacturing process show strong evidence, that the new smart clothing manufacturing process must be structured in a similar way to the modern clothing manufacturing technology, in which **multiple pipelined steps are separated and isolated from each another**, thus promoting parallel and separated innovation in each of those steps without too many cross-constraints complicating the manufacturing process chain.

This means, that the manufacturing steps must be separated with interdependence between them minimized as much as possible. This is needed both for compatibility with existing manufacturing processes and for easier innovation in the unsolved problems in physical smart textile manufacturing process. Such innovation is really important in at least these two areas of research: resistance to washing and resistance to bending and stretching. The current process of manufacturing interconnect at the same time as the smart clothing with complicated dependencies has not led to durable and washable smart clothing currently. By separating these manufacturing steps, the experts at resilience and washability of electronics components can work separately from the smart clothing designers, and thus focus more with less complex inter-process interactions with the smart clothing development forming a perpetual circular innovation process[198]. This would allow more organizations and individuals to work on these complex problems in parallel [199], and as a result more washable

and robust smart clothing might be achievable sooner and with less waste in the development process.

Another key issue in developing this new standard is flexibility in design. The reason is, that smart clothing must also serve as clothing, with all its functional, artistic and stylistic needs in addition to its electronics/smart goals, if it is to be successful [200]. Thus, **the new standard must be flexible enough for clothing designers** - the designers must be able to freely choose the placement of actuators and sensors, the form and feel of the clothing as well as its physical properties.

It means, that the interconnect **fabric must be standardized in a way, that guarantees rather high probability of any useful sensor placement to actually be connectable to the interconnect** - even if it is cut and sewn as any normal textile would be in the clothing manufacturing process.

Another key concern, that relates to sustainability is the economy of used materials. There is a tradeoff in supporting very dense sensor placement options, which require more material for interconnect (e.g. copper/conductive yarn) - this becomes more wasteful, but also more economically unfeasible, as the interconnect technologies are usually prohibitively costly. Thus the previous requirement must be balanced with another requirement - **to minimize the use of potentially expensive conductive materials in the interconnect**.

These last two requirements are opposite and conflicting by nature, and thus the solution is to use optimization methods in order to find an optimal/balanced trade-off point. This point might differ for different smart clothing applications, thus the standard will have separate implementation guidelines developed which will guide the implementer **in choosing a balance between the cost, material usage and guarantees for sensor and actuator placement**. These guidelines will provide guidance in decision making for selection of most appropriate configurations in the specific applications.

2.2 Proposed methodology

Based on the previously discussed we have outlined the standardized steps for smart clothing manufacturing process below (see Figure 2.1) [201]:

1. Fabric rolls with an integrated universal wiring grid streamline the manufacturing process by replacing the traditional fabric selection and sourcing step. This innovation fits seamlessly into existing manufacturing technologies, simplifying the integration of smart textiles and enhancing the efficiency of smart clothing production (Section 1.3, step 2);
2. The garments are subsequently tailored, produced, and sized in accordance with contemporary clothing manufacturing technologies (Section 1.3) - no change needed for steps 3 (accessory selection), 4 (sizing and fit), 5 (pattern construction) and 6 (fabric spreading and cutting);
3. During the seventh step of the current manufacturing process, known as fabric-joining, additional connectors are incorporated as needed to link

Figure 2.1: Proposed standardized steps for smart clothing manufacturing process [201]

wiring between separate cut components, such as attaching sleeves to the torso of a shirt;

4. In the garment finishing phase, which is the eighth step of the manufacturing process, a connector or pocket is incorporated to house a module containing a battery and a wireless communication unit;
5. In the same step, sensor nodes are selected and strategically placed at appropriate locations on the finished garment, transforming it into a functional sensor network;
6. During the ninth step, which involves quality control and assurance, the entire garment undergoes comprehensive testing. Self-diagnosis and mapping are conducted to determine the optimal wiring for power, data, and clock signal delivery, ensuring that all components function correctly;
7. Following the completion of the final touches, which is the tenth step of the manufacturing process, the smart clothing is dispatched to the user. Along with the garment, the user receives software that enables them to configure the required functionalities of the garment, such as loading sensor or actuator drivers across the entire sensor network for seamless integration;
8. Finally, the data collected from the sensor network is aggregated and potentially pre-processed by the main communication module. This data is then wirelessly transmitted to a computer or mobile device, where additional software can be deployed to address specific use-case requirements.

A short overview of how this new standardized process aligns with or contradicts the modern clothing manufacturing technology (Section 1.3) is shown below in Table 2.1.

2.2.1 Changes to step "fabric selection and sourcing"

This change in the current modern clothing manufacturing technology is the most impactful. This change requires new e-textile fabric to be developed and manufactured, but also provides the biggest benefit - the complete decoupling of the smart clothing manufacturing process steps and development of innovative smart wiring interconnects.

There are many potential universal smart clothing interconnect manufacturing technologies as described in Section 1.3. This means, that whenever demand for such fabric will rise enough, it can be assumed that one of them will be successfully developed into the required interconnect fabric with enough investments, which instead will serve as an input into the proposed smart clothing manufacturing process.

Still, before such universal interconnect fabric is developed (irrespective of the specific technology) **a key aspect that needs to be solved - the**

Original step	Changes	Details
1. Planning	No change	-
2. Fabric selection and sourcing	Replaced (See section 2.2.1)	New fabric manufactured
3. Garment accessory, trim and closure selection	No change	-
4. Garment sizing and fit	No change	-
5. Pattern construction	No change	-
6. Fabric spreading and cutting	No change	-
7. Fabric-joining	Updated (See section 2.2.2)	Wire joining procedure added
8. Garment finishing	Updated (See section 2.2.3)	Sensor node and base station connection step added
9. Quality control and quality assurance	Updated (See section 2.2.4)	Wiring mapping and testing procedure added
10. Final touches	No change	-

Table 2.1: Proposed changes in the steps of modern clothing manufacturing technology

configuration of the wiring network in this interconnect fabric. To select such wiring configuration we must optimize for the requirements as shown in Section 2.1, with emphasis on:

- **Sustainability** - the interconnect network must to minimize the amount used of potentially expensive and non-sustainable wiring materials, as well as minimize unusable parts of this material, due to it potentially being unreachable on the smart clothing items produced.
- **Flexibility in design** - the freedom of clothing designers should not be limited by the the wiring network, so that wires can be cut as needed and can still reach the required sensor and actuator locations on the clothing item designed.

The interconnect configuration - specifically the size and pattern of the wiring - will dictate the locations where sensors and actuators can be attached, as well as where and how the final interconnect fabric can be cut, how much waste it will produce and how the pieces can be connected together again. Thus, a critical part of this proposed process is the identification of **the optimal pattern and configuration of the universal fabric interconnect**. As the choice of the wiring pattern and configuration can change based on the specific business requirements, this point will be elaborated in the implementation guidelines section, with available options laid out for potentially different scenarios.

Figure 2.2: Illustration of interconnect joint jumpers

When the appropriate configuration and wiring pattern is selected, the appropriate interconnect fabric can then be chosen as part of the existing fabric selection and sourcing process step, and thus perfectly integrates in the modern clothing manufacturing technology.

2.2.2 Changes to step "fabric-jointing"

First the normal step of fabric jointing process is executed as in the ordinary modern clothing manufacturing technology. Then an additional procedure for wire joining must be added, in order to guarantee, that all required sensor and actuator locations on the smart clothing are actually reachable after the cutting of the interconnect fabric. This involves adding of special "jumper" connections to the jointed seams in select locations, that would connect the pieces of interconnect on two separate parts of fabric as illustrated in Figure 2.2.

Due to the fact that clothing joints usually don't need to be as elastic as the clothing itself, the jumpers can be created either from the elastic wiring material from the interconnect, or using any other classic wiring technologies. The specific number and configuration of these jumpers is dependent on the specific interconnect wiring pattern and configuration, and thus will also be elaborated in the implementation guidelines later. The main steps in this process will include the redundancy analysis of the specific garment in order to determine the number, size and placement of the jumpers as appropriate.

2.2.3 Changes to step "garment finishing"

Most of the garment finishing steps are executed as normal. Additional step is added to connect the sensor, actuator, data gathering and transmission nodes to the smart clothing being manufactured. Each of these nodes is an electronic device, that requires connection to the universal interconnect and need to be affixed to the fabric of the clothing it self at specific locations. The specific attachment technology might vary - sewing as buttons, placing them in specialized pockets, gluing/laminating/coating with specialized compounds,

protecting them from moisture and wear etc. Due to the fact that this step is completely dependent on the final smart clothing product and its goals, the specific implementation of this step is left to the implementer.

In cases, where the universal interconnect does not connect to the specific location where connection is needed, additional jumper wires similar to those described above, can be used to connect them to the closest point of interconnect. The specifics of these connections are also very implementation specific and will be discussed in the implementation guidelines.

An additional step, that might need to be done here, depending on the needs of the smart clothing is related to adding specialized routing nodes to the interconnect in cases where bus connection is not appropriate, so that signals and/or power can be routed in specific directions.

2.2.4 Changes to step "Quality control and quality assurance"

In addition to the original activities in the quality control and quality assurance step, there are two more steps that need to be included in the clothing manufacturing process:

- the locations of connected devices must be determined on the smart clothing item either by mapping of the wiring or determining the location continuity in some other way. This step is also important for potentially reprogramming the electronics nodes later while in the smart clothing network. Some additional routing decisions might also be enacted here for better efficiency;
- Final testing of the smart clothing in order to determine, that all connected sensors and actuators are connected correctly and that routing and redundancy of the network match the needs of the final smart clothing item.

As the mapping and testing steps depend on the final configuration and pattern of the universal interconnect, the specifics will also be discussed in the implementation guidelines. It also must be noted, that these steps can be different depending on the required optimization level for a specific smart clothing product. This means, that a more detailed description and implementation of these steps can be left as a future research topic and thus only partially will be explored in this project - some prototype algorithms will be developed to validate this concept during the project.

2.2.5 Additional concerns for standardized smart clothing production

For completeness sake one additional step must be mentioned that is out of scope of the clothing manufacturing technology itself, but is already done for all existing smart clothing items after they are manufactured and will be needed here as well. When the smart clothing item is finalized using the described approach, end user software for this clothing item must also be developed, including such

aspects as interaction with the clothing, gathering and visualization of data from it etc.

2.3 Implementation guidelines

Due to the fact that the project is ongoing, the final implementation guidelines are still under the development as they are based on the validation steps of the process, that take place in the next stages of the project. These guidelines will be available as a separate document when ready.

2.4 Sustainability of the proposed methodology

As mentioned above **Sustainability** is a critical consideration for this proposed methodology. Any processes that force replacement of existing equipment will have major environmental impact on such a scale, which might also impede adoption of such a standard due to climate change considerations and legislation. Even though other approaches for reducing the environmental effect of smart textiles are being explored, such as circular economy and recycling [174], the environmental impact of clothing manufacturing processes cannot be underestimated [194], and when innovations are applied with care, even the growth of textile and clothing manufacturing industry, can lead to reduction in carbon-dioxide emissions[195]. In order to make a supply chain for smart clothing sustainable, it has to be built on a closed-loop mode that starts from material production and ends with recycling [196]. It has taken a lot of resources and time to move the classic clothing industry towards these goals, thus, reuse of any part of this supply chain will greatly reduce the investments needed to make smart clothing manufacturing sustainable. The proposed methodology minimizes the changes to the established clothing manufacturing process, thus minimizing environmental costs of the process implementation.

At the same time the discreet and defined steps of the improved process allow for additional process optimization at every step – for example, the material and wiring embedding process can be optimized on an industrial scale, where each sustainability improvement and cost reduction scales and motivates the manufacturer as opposed to the existing processes, where each specific item of smart clothing is a small scale manufacturing with many inefficiencies and the low amount of items produced does not support optimizations of mass production, thus more wasteful processes were forced to be used.

The methodology defines a manufacturing process in which the core improvement is based on the use and configuration of the interconnect fabric, which allows for incremental improvements in the discreet manufacturing steps. The new process allows for previously impossible sustainability improvements in the smart clothing manufacturing process itself. Specifically, because many different manufacturers are currently forced to reinvent the wheel and use unique non-standardized low-yield processes for each smart clothing item type manufacturing. This means more material waste due to lack of scale and high

amount of manufacturing failures due to unreliable and even manual processes. This also means, that during the manufacturing the smart clothing items might need to be shipped long distances between different specialists (clothing, wiring, fashion, electronics, sensors, washability etc.) introducing environmental costs of this extra shipping. This can be solved by allowing for universal adaptation of complex and highly resilient wearable interconnect technologies as well as development of new even better ones, while allowing the manufacturers of smart clothing to spend less time, effort and materials in order to develop new smart clothing items with unique and useful functionality [63]. This problem is exacerbated even more by the fact that the existing clothing manufacturing industry is very large in the scale of investments and equipment deployed - on the trillion-dollar scale (1.53 trillion USD in 2022[189]), thus each new type of manufacturing process for smart clothing necessitates a lot of replaced and adjusted equipment leading to even more waste. The implementation of this proposed standard allows for optimization in each standardized step and removes the overlap of specialties required for manufacturing a new type of smart clothing – existing clothing experts can keep their work processes and machinery, and only some steps of the conventional clothing manufacturing process need to be updated for the new process to work. Each of these isolated steps can then be optimized in order to maximize the sustainability of smart clothing manufacturing in the future. The simulations and prototypes for the process validation developed in this project also allow us to provide specific guidelines to implement the process appropriately with most sustainability in mind for a specific application/production of smart clothing.

Chapter 3

Verification and validation

Due to the fact, that this methodology aims at completely new wearables manufacturing process, the actual process will not be fully implemented during the project and will instead be developed as a theoretical framework with limited proof-of-concept piloting instead. Thus, only the plausibility of implementation will be validated through practical implementation in pilot (creation of interconnect fabric, cutting and sewing the fabric into a wearable form, adding wearable sensor nodes and interconnecting the data flows). The rest of the testing of this methodology takes place as computer simulation in order to prove the efficiency and sustainability of the interconnect approach.

3.1 Methodology

The first plausibility tests have been done in the lab in a small scale with a simple wired data and power transmission proof of concept. Further physical process validation will be done in the next iterations of pilot prototypes.

Additionally, the efficiency and sustainability of the approach has been analysed using computer simulations. Specifically, to determine answers to the following questions:

- What is the overall plausibility of implementation of this process?
- What is the reachability of any randomly placed wearable node on the interconnect?
- What is the percentage of useful vs redundant interconnect lanes in any random wearable configuration?
- What is the average length and number of jumps in the interconnect between any two random wearable nodes?
- What is the efficiency of use of the interconnect material (e.g. copper)

3.1.1 Simulations

In order to answer the previously defined questions a set of simulations was developed. The simulation methodology contained the following steps, as described next.

3.1.1.1 Generation and marking of clothing items

In order to prove, that any specific topology of smart textile wiring can provide useful results for a wide variety of real-world smart clothing applications, we first need to develop a representative set of clothing item schematics, that can be simulated to be cut and sewn from each of the smart textile configurations being analyzed.

A selection of **17 different clothing designs** was selected as follows (the selection was limited to the available schematics, but wide enough to cover main types of clothing that might be used as smart clothing):

- Male garments:
 - Fitted T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - * with V-neck, short arms
 - * with V-neck, long arms
 - Wide cut T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - Jacket/Hoodie
 - Shorts
- Female garments:
 - Fitted T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - * with V-neck, short arms
 - * with V-neck, long arms
 - Wide cut T-shirt:
 - * with U-neck, short arms
 - * with U-neck, long arms
 - Jacket/Hoodie
 - Shorts
 - Pants/Leggings

Figure 3.1: Example of clothing schematic used in simulation

Figure 3.2: Example of marked sewn joint in clothing schematic

An example clothing schematic (Male T-Shirt with Long Arms) can be seen in Figure 3.1.

For each of these clothing schematics not only all cuts were defined, but also the edges that need to be sewn together on each of the cut pieces were marked (see Figure 3.2), so that during the simulation the actual connectivity across the connections of multiple pieces of smart textile can be evaluated, not only each piece by itself.

Each clothing item was then generated into **10 different sizes** according to European standard BSI, 2004. BS EN 13402-3:2004 "Size Designation of Clothes - Part 3: Measurements and Intervals" as shown in Table 3.1.

Thus in total for simulations $17 * 10 = 170$ **different clothing schematics** were prepared.

Size	Male Chest circumference	Female Chest circumference
XXS	70–78	66–74
XS	78–86	74–82
S	86–94	82–90
M	94–102	90–98
L	102–110	98–107
XL	110–118	107–119
XXL	118–129	119–131
3XL	129–141	131–143
4XL	141–154	143–155
5XL	154–166	155–167

Table 3.1: Different clothing sizes (in mm) used for simulations

3.1.1.2 Selection of candidate wiring schematics for simulation

In order to simulate different applicable wiring patterns for smart textiles, representative and useful patterns must be selected first. Due to the fact, that one of the goals is sustainability and thus minimization of wiring material used, it must be noted, that **all wire segments should be straight** as that is the shortest route between two points and thus yields the shortest wire length. Also, due to the fact, that the process must be applicable to all kinds of clothing, without any preference for specific cutting schematics and rotations, the **pattern should be symmetrical rotationally**, which means that **all wire segments should be of the same length**.

As the wiring pattern in total can be looked at as a tessellation of the plane of the smart textile, and more specifically, we are interested in the wires (edges) not the tessellating figures themselves. When looking at a rotationally symmetrical group of wires/edges, we can look at the vertex connecting those edges, and thus analyze the patterns based on the vertexes and how many of these equal length wires connect to them at what angles. The vertex symmetry of interest is called isogonality.

As there are an infinite number of such tessellations or wire patterns possible, so some additional constraints must be added. The tessellations must not "waste" wires, by having concave tessellation shapes. When evaluating a type of tessellation, that matches all these requirements, it was determined, that a good candidate is equilateral monogonal tessellations. There are 11 Archimedean (semi-regular) tessellations forming only regular shapes such as squares etc. (a more detailed description of the choice is available in [202]), so a selection of tessellation shapes with these properties were chosen as shown in Figure 3.3. Each of the tessellation patterns has a name with numbers separated with points, where the numbers mean what shape connects to the vertex (e.g. 3=triangle, 4=square, 6=hexagon). Thus a 6.6.6 pattern means that each vertex connects to 3 regular hexagons, while 4.4.4.4 pattern means that each vertex connects to 4 squares. Some regular shapes can be arranged in multiple ways around a vertex forming a different tessellation pattern - two additional such modifications

Figure 3.3: Selected wiring patterns/tesselations for simulation

were found for the pattern 4.6.12 and those are marked with additional letters "a" and "b" accordingly, resulting in $11 + 2 = 13$ **different wiring patterns** selected for simulations.

The minimum and maximum length of those wire segments must also be determined for the simulations. Most clothing is either for top or bottom half of the human body, and a reasonable maximum human height is about 2 meters, thus, half of that or 1 meter is a reasonable upper limit for a height of a clothing item, and thus a piece of smart textile needed for it. As humans are usually not wider than a meter, we can assume for simplicities sake, that the maximum dimensions of a piece of smart textile needed for human clothing should be about 1m by 1m or 1000mm by 1000mm. Because of this a single wire should be somewhere between 0mm and 1000mm based on the number of sensor attachment points that might be needed across the smart clothing item. We can assume, that it is possible to connect a sensor or actuator module to the wires on smart clothing with some sort of minimal length of connector - for the simulation we assume that this connector/jumper wire can be up to 10mm long. From that the minimum wire length can be assumed double that due to the fact, that if a node is connected between two ends of the shortest wire, these jumper wires could still connect to at least one of the ends. Thus, the **minimum wire length used in simulations is 20mm**. On the other hand, the maximum wire length should be no longer than any reasonable distance between two wearable sensors on potential smart clothing. A typical human motion analysis application might require a sensor per each large human joint (e.g. one on lower and upper arm respectively). On most humans this distance falls somewhere between 150mm-

Figure 3.4: Examples of jumper wires for smart textiles (green) connecting wires between multiple parts of clothing or wires to sensor nodes (blue)

300mm. In order to be conservative, for the simulations we target the lower end of this distance, so around 150mm. In order to reduce the simulation calculation length, we can use a doubling scale for the wire lengths - thus starting from 20mm, we can double the lengths to 40mm, 80mm and finally 160mm (around 150mm mentioned before). This leads to **4 different wire lengths** to be used for simulation.

As a result the simulation has $13 * 4 = 52$ **different wiring patterns in multiple wire lengths**. In order to run simulations for each wire pattern on each selected clothing schematic, we need to run $52 * 170 = 8840$ **different simulated experiments**.

3.1.1.3 Simulation methodology

To finalize the number of simulated experiments to be run, one more parameter must be determined - the allowable distance between a sensor and wire or between two wires across two sewn together pieces of fabric, referred to as jumper length (see Figure ??). As discussed before, the minimum reasonable jumper length can be assumed to be 10mm. The maximum jumper length should not be reasonably longer than, the maximum wire length, so using the same doubling approach as for wire length, we can arrive at the following **5 jumper lengths** to be used in the simulations: 10mm, 20mm, 40mm, 80mm and 160mm.

Finally, we can define our experimental simulation parameter space for each simulated experiment with each jumper length to be $8840 * 5 = 44200$ **different simulations to be run**.

For each of these simulations then results will be aggregated and analyzed in

order to select the most appropriate wiring configurations.

3.2 Verification results

The verification results will be published as a separate document and reported in project deliverable D1.6 "Material and process validation and testing results" after the verification steps will be finished.

Bibliography

- [1] Elise Saoutieff, Tiziana Polichetti, Laurent Jouanet, Adrien Faucon, Audrey Vidal, Alexandre Pereira, Sébastien Boisseau, Thomas Ernst, Maria Lucia Miglietta, Brigida Alfano, et al. A wearable low-power sensing platform for environmental and health monitoring: The convergence project. *Sensors*, 21(5):1802, 2021.
- [2] Jonathan Tyler, Sung Won Choi, and Muneesh Tewari. Real-time, personalized medicine through wearable sensors and dynamic predictive modeling: a new paradigm for clinical medicine. *Current opinion in systems biology*, 20:17–25, 2020.
- [3] Carissa A Low. Harnessing consumer smartphone and wearable sensors for clinical cancer research. *npj Digital Medicine*, 3(1):140, 2020.
- [4] Shyamal Patel, Hyung Park, Paolo Bonato, Leighton Chan, and Mary Rodgers. A review of wearable sensors and systems with application in rehabilitation. *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation*, 9(1):1–17, 2012.
- [5] Qi Wang, Panos Markopoulos, Bin Yu, Wei Chen, and Annick Timmermans. Interactive wearable systems for upper body rehabilitation: a systematic review. *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation*, 14(1):1–21, 2017.
- [6] Issam Boukhenoufa, Xiaojun Zhai, Victor Utti, Jo Jackson, and Klaus D McDonald-Maier. Wearable sensors and machine learning in post-stroke rehabilitation assessment: A systematic review. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 71:103197, 2022.
- [7] Ruiyang Yin, Depeng Wang, Shufang Zhao, Zheng Lou, and Guozhen Shen. Wearable sensors-enabled human-machine interaction systems: from design to application. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 31(11):2008936, 2021.
- [8] Armands Ancans, Artis Rozentals, Krisjanis Nesenbergs, and Modris Greitans. Inertial sensors and muscle electrical signals in human-computer interaction. In *2017 6th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology and Accessibility (ICTA)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2017.

- [9] Zhiwei Lin, Gaoqiang Zhang, Xiao Xiao, Christian Au, Yihao Zhou, Chenchen Sun, Zhihao Zhou, Rong Yan, Endong Fan, Shaobo Si, et al. A personalized acoustic interface for wearable human–machine interaction. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 32(9):2109430, 2022.
- [10] Changbum R Ahn, SangHyun Lee, Cenfei Sun, Houtan Jebelli, Kanghyeok Yang, and Byungjoo Choi. Wearable sensing technology applications in construction safety and health. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 145(11):03119007, 2019.
- [11] Chukwuma Nnaji, Ifeanyi Okpala, and Ibukun Awolusi. Wearable sensing devices: Potential impact & current use for incident prevention. *Professional safety*, 65(04):16–24, 2020.
- [12] Carolin Helbig, Maximilian Ueberham, Anna Maria Becker, Heike Marquart, and Uwe Schlink. Wearable sensors for human environmental exposure in urban settings. *Current Pollution Reports*, 7(3):417–433, 2021.
- [13] Dhruv R Seshadri, Ryan T Li, James E Voos, James R Rowbottom, Celeste M Alfes, Christian A Zorman, and Colin K Drummond. Wearable sensors for monitoring the internal and external workload of the athlete. *NPJ digital medicine*, 2(1):71, 2019.
- [14] Ryan T Li, Scott R Kling, Michael J Salata, Sean A Cupp, Joseph Sheehan, and James E Voos. Wearable performance devices in sports medicine. *Sports health*, 8(1):74–78, 2016.
- [15] LJ Elstubb, CA Nurse, LM Grohowski, P Volgyesi, DN Wolf, and KE Zelik. Tibial bone forces can be monitored using shoe-worn wearable sensors during running. *Journal of sports sciences*, 40(15):1741–1749, 2022.
- [16] Thanos G Stavropoulos, Asterios Papastergiou, Lampros Mpaltadoros, Spiros Nikolopoulos, and Ioannis Kompatsiaris. Iot wearable sensors and devices in elderly care: A literature review. *Sensors*, 20(10):2826, 2020.
- [17] Anita Ramachandran, Anupama Karuppiah, et al. A survey on recent advances in wearable fall detection systems. *BioMed research international*, 2020, 2020.
- [18] Santhosha Rao. Iot enabled wearable device for covid safety and emergencies. 2021.
- [19] Juliane R Sempionatto, Victor Ruiz-Valdepenas Montiel, Eva Vargas, Hazhir Teymourian, and Joseph Wang. Wearable and mobile sensors for personalized nutrition. *ACS sensors*, 6(5):1745–1760, 2021.
- [20] Mustafa Degerli and Sevgi Ozkan Yildirim. Enablers for iot regarding wearable medical devices to support healthy living: The five facets. In *IoT in Healthcare and Ambient Assisted Living*, pages 201–222. Springer, 2021.

- [21] Massimiliano De Zambotti, Nicola Cellini, Aimee Goldstone, Ian M Colrain, and Fiona C Baker. Wearable sleep technology in clinical and research settings. *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 51(7):1538, 2019.
- [22] Francesco Miele and Lia Tirabeni. Digital technologies and power dynamics in the organization: A conceptual review of remote working and wearable technologies at work. *Sociology Compass*, 14(6):e12795, 2020.
- [23] Martin Krzywdzinski, Sabine Pfeiffer, Maren Evers, and Christine Gerber. Measuring work and workers: wearables and digital assistance systems in manufacturing and logistics. 2022.
- [24] Kateryna Maltseva. Wearables in the workplace: The brave new world of employee engagement. *Business Horizons*, 63(4):493–505, 2020.
- [25] Debasish Bal, Md Munirul Islam Tusher, Mizanur Rahman, and Md Salmanur Rahman Saymon. Navix: a wearable navigation system for visually impaired persons. In *2020 2nd International Conference on Sustainable Technologies for Industry 4.0 (STI)*, pages 1–4. IEEE, 2020.
- [26] Julio S Lora-Millan, Gabriel Delgado-Oleas, Julián Benito-León, and Eduardo Rocon. A review on wearable technologies for tremor suppression. *Frontiers in neurology*, 12:700600, 2021.
- [27] Antonio Rodríguez-Fernández, Joan Lobo-Prat, and Josep M Font-Llagunes. Systematic review on wearable lower-limb exoskeletons for gait training in neuromuscular impairments. *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation*, 18(1):1–21, 2021.
- [28] Prithu Bhatnagar, Sadeq Hooshmand Zaferani, Nassim Rafiefard, Bardia Baraeinejad, Amir Reza Vazifeh, Raheleh Mohammadpour, Reza Ghomashchi, Harald Dillersberger, Douglas Tham, and Daryoosh Vashae. Advancing personalized healthcare and entertainment: Progress in energy harvesting materials and techniques of self-powered wearable devices. *Progress in Materials Science*, page 101184, 2023.
- [29] Min Chen, Yingying Jiang, Yong Cao, and Albert Y Zomaya. Creativebioman: a brain-and body-wearable, computing-based, creative gaming system. *IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Magazine*, 6(1):14–22, 2020.
- [30] Francesco Vona, Silvia Silleresi, Eleonora Beccaluva, and Franca Garzotto. Social matchup: Collaborative games in wearable virtual reality for persons with neurodevelopmental disorders. In *Joint International Conference on Serious Games*, pages 49–65. Springer, 2020.
- [31] Muhammet Ramoğlu. Cyborg-computer interaction: Designing new senses. *The Design Journal*, 22(sup1):1215–1225, 2019.

- [32] Doruk Yildirim, Luis Edgardo Fraguada, and Elizabeth Esther Bigger. Dualskin: Ambient electric field sensing wearable. In *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM International Symposium on Wearable Computers*, pages 339–345, 2019.
- [33] Marko Nardini. Merging familiar and new senses to perceive and act in space. *Cognitive Processing*, 22(Suppl 1):69–75, 2021.
- [34] Shu-Wen Hsu and Ta-Te Lin. Development and assessment of a wearable waist-assistive exoskeleton for agricultural tasks. In *2021 ASABE Annual International Virtual Meeting*, page 1. American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers, 2021.
- [35] Carly Thalman and Panagiotis Artemiadis. A review of soft wearable robots that provide active assistance: Trends, common actuation methods, fabrication, and applications. *Wearable Technologies*, 1:e3, 2020.
- [36] Domenico Prattichizzo, Maria Pozzi, Tommaso Lisini Baldi, Monica Malvezzi, Irfan Hussain, Simone Rossi, and Gionata Salvietti. Human augmentation by wearable supernumerary robotic limbs: review and perspectives. *Progress in Biomedical Engineering*, 3(4):042005, 2021.
- [37] Philip Jovanovic and Robin Kay. Examining the use of wearable technologies for k-12 students: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Digital Life and Learning*, 1(1):56–67, 2021.
- [38] George Koutromanos and Georgia Kazakou. The use of smart wearables in primary and secondary education: A systematic review. *Themes in eLearning*, 13:33–53, 2020.
- [39] Xin Zhao and Lin Cong. Effect of problem and scripting-based learning combining wearable technology on orthopedic operating room nurses’ learning outcomes. *Nurse Education Today*, 73:13–16, 2019.
- [40] Bas Van Hooren, Jos Goudsmit, Juan Restrepo, and Steven Vos. Real-time feedback by wearables in running: Current approaches, challenges and suggestions for improvements. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 38(2):214–230, 2020.
- [41] Vaithinathan Karthikeyan, James Utama Surjadi, Joseph CK Wong, Venkataraman Kannan, Kwok-Ho Lam, Xianfeng Chen, Yang Lu, and Vellaisamy AL Roy. Wearable and flexible thin film thermoelectric module for multi-scale energy harvesting. *Journal of Power Sources*, 455:227983, 2020.
- [42] Xiayue Fan, Bin Liu, Jia Ding, Yida Deng, Xiaopeng Han, Wenbin Hu, and Cheng Zhong. Flexible and wearable power sources for next-generation wearable electronics. *Batteries & Supercaps*, 3(12):1262–1274, 2020.

- [43] Carlos A Tavera, Jesús H Ortiz, Osamah I Khalaf, Diego F Saavedra, Theyazn HH Aldhyani, et al. Wearable wireless body area networks for medical applications. *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine*, 2021, 2021.
- [44] Kenneth R. Foster and John Torous. The opportunity and obstacles for smartwatches and wearable sensors. *IEEE Pulse*, 10(1):22–25, 2019.
- [45] Sen Qiu, Hongkai Zhao, Nan Jiang, Zhelong Wang, Long Liu, Yi An, Hongyu Zhao, Xin Miao, Ruichen Liu, and Giancarlo Fortino. Multi-sensor information fusion based on machine learning for real applications in human activity recognition: State-of-the-art and research challenges. *Information Fusion*, 80:241–265, 2022.
- [46] Brooke M Bell, Ridwan Alam, Nabil Alshurafa, Edison Thomaz, Abu S Mondol, Kayla de la Haye, John A Stankovic, John Lach, and Donna Spruijt-Metz. Automatic, wearable-based, in-field eating detection approaches for public health research: a scoping review. *NPJ digital medicine*, 3(1):38, 2020.
- [47] Srikanth Sagar Bangaru, Chao Wang, Sri Aditya Busam, and Fereydoun Aghazadeh. Ann-based automated scaffold builder activity recognition through wearable emg and imu sensors. *Automation in Construction*, 126:103653, 2021.
- [48] Yun-Hsuan Chen and Mohamad Sawan. Trends and challenges of wearable multimodal technologies for stroke risk prediction. *Sensors*, 21(2):460, 2021.
- [49] Md Moniruzzaman, Zhaozheng Yin, Md Sanzid Bin Hossain, Hwan Choi, and Zhishan Guo. Wearable motion capture: Reconstructing and predicting 3d human poses from wearable sensors. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 2023.
- [50] Armands Ancans, Modris Greitans, Ricards Cacurs, Beate Banga, and Artis Rozentals. Wearable sensor clothing for body movement measurement during physical activities in healthcare. *Sensors*, 21(6):2068, 2021.
- [51] Ya Huang, Kuanming Yao, Jiyu Li, Dengfeng Li, Huiling Jia, Yiming Liu, Chun Ki Yiu, Wooyoung Park, and Xinge Yu. Recent advances in multi-mode haptic feedback technologies towards wearable interfaces. *Materials Today Physics*, 22:100602, 2022.
- [52] Arata Horie, Yunao Zheng, and Masahiko Inami. A wearable system integrating force myography and skin stretch feedback toward force skill learning. In *2023 IEEE World Haptics Conference (WHC)*, pages 190–196. IEEE, 2023.

- [53] Erika Covi, Elisa Donati, Xiangpeng Liang, David Kappel, Hadi Heidari, Melika Payvand, and Wei Wang. Adaptive extreme edge computing for wearable devices. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 15:611300, 2021.
- [54] Dr V Suma. Wearable iot based distributed framework for ubiquitous computing. *Journal of Ubiquitous Computing and Communication Technologies*, 3(1):23–32, 2021.
- [55] Min Chen, Sergio Gonzalez, Athanasios Vasilakos, Huasong Cao, and Victor CM Leung. Body area networks: A survey. *Mobile networks and applications*, 16:171–193, 2011.
- [56] Samaneh Movassaghi, Mehran Abolhasan, Justin Lipman, David Smith, and Abbas Jamalipour. Wireless body area networks: A survey. *IEEE Communications surveys & tutorials*, 16(3):1658–1686, 2014.
- [57] Carmen CY Poon, Benny PL Lo, Mehmet Rasit Yuce, Akram Alomainy, and Yang Hao. Body sensor networks: In the era of big data and beyond. *IEEE reviews in biomedical engineering*, 8:4–16, 2015.
- [58] Gengfa Fang, Eryk Dutkiewicz, Mohammad A Huq, Rein Vesilo, and Yihuai Yang. Medical body area networks: opportunities, challenges and practices. In *2011 11th International Symposium on Communications & Information Technologies (ISCIT)*, pages 562–567. IEEE, 2011.
- [59] Thoams Guthrie Zimmerman. Personal area networks: Near-field intrabody communication. *IBM systems Journal*, 35(3.4):609–617, 1996.
- [60] Karen Van Dam, Steve Pitchers, and Mike Barnard. From pan to ban: Why body area networks. In *Proceedings of the Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF) Second Meeting*, pages 10–11, 2001.
- [61] Ieee standard for local and metropolitan area networks - part 15.6: Wireless body area networks. *IEEE Std 802.15.6-2012*, pages 1–271, 2012.
- [62] Heribert Baldus, Steven Corroy, Alberto Fazzi, Karin Klabunde, and Tim Schenk. Human-centric connectivity enabled by body-coupled communications. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 47(6):172–178, 2009.
- [63] Gilsoo Cho. *Smart clothing: technology and applications*. CRC press, 2009.
- [64] Ren Xiangfang, Shen Lei, Liu Miaomiao, Zhang Xiying, and Chen Han. Research and sustainable design of wearable sensor for clothing based on body area network. *Cognitive Computation and Systems*, 3(3):206–220, 2021.
- [65] Tünde Kirstein, Didier Cottet, Janusz Grzyb, and Gerhard Tröster. Wearable computing systems—electronic textiles. *Wearable electronics and photonics*, pages 177–197, 2005.

- [66] Xiaoming Tao. *Smart fibres, fabrics and clothing: fundamentals and applications*. Elsevier, 2001.
- [67] Gilsoo Cho, Seungsin Lee, and Jayoung Cho. Review and reappraisal of smart clothing. *International journal of human-computer interaction*, 25(6):582–617, 2009.
- [68] Kaspar MB Jansen. How to shape the future of smart clothing. In *Adjunct Proceedings of the 2019 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing and Proceedings of the 2019 ACM International Symposium on Wearable Computers*, pages 1037–1039, 2019.
- [69] Xiaoming Tao. *Handbook of smart textiles*. Springer Singapore, 2015.
- [70] Stefan Schneegass and Oliver Amft. *Smart textiles*. Springer, 2017.
- [71] Rebecca R Ruckdashel, Ninad Khadse, and Jay Hoon Park. Smart e-textiles: overview of components and outlook. *Sensors*, 22(16):6055, 2022.
- [72] Lina M Castano and Alison B Flatau. Smart fabric sensors and e-textile technologies: a review. *Smart Materials and structures*, 23(5):053001, 2014.
- [73] Heloisa Ramlow, Karina Luzia Andrade, and Ana Paula Serafini Immich. Smart textiles: An overview of recent progress on chromic textiles. *The journal of the textile institute*, 112(1):152–171, 2021.
- [74] Binghao Wang and Antonio Facchetti. Mechanically flexible conductors for stretchable and wearable e-skin and e-textile devices. *Advanced Materials*, 31(28):1901408, 2019.
- [75] Xinlong Sun, Jun-Heng Fu, Chao Teng, MingKuan Zhang, TianYing Liu, MingHui Guo, Peng Qin, Fei Zhan, Yan Ren, Hongbin Zhao, et al. Superhydrophobic e-textile with an ag-egain conductive layer for motion detection and electromagnetic interference shielding. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 14(29):33650–33661, 2022.
- [76] Xianghui Zeng, Minglu Hu, Pei He, Weikai Zhao, Sihan Dong, Xiaowen Xu, Guozhang Dai, Jia Sun, and Junliang Yang. Highly conductive carbon-based e-textile for gesture recognition. *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, 44(5):825–828, 2023.
- [77] Hualing He, Jinru Liu, Yushu Wang, Yuhang Zhao, Yi Qin, Zhenyu Zhu, Zhicai Yu, and Jinfeng Wang. An ultralight self-powered fire alarm e-textile based on conductive aerogel fiber with repeatable temperature monitoring performance used in firefighting clothing. *ACS nano*, 16(2):2953–2967, 2022.
- [78] Gopika Rajan, Joseph J Morgan, Conor Murphy, Elias Torres Alonso, Jessica Wade, Anna K Ott, Saverio Russo, Helena Alves, Monica F Craciun, and Ana IS Neves. Low operating voltage carbon-graphene

- hybrid e-textile for temperature sensing. *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, 12(26):29861–29867, 2020.
- [79] Young-Eun Shin, Joon Young Cho, Jeonghee Yeom, Hyunhyub Ko, and Joong Tark Han. Electronic textiles based on highly conducting poly (vinyl alcohol)/carbon nanotube/silver nanobelt hybrid fibers. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 13(26):31051–31058, 2021.
- [80] Ozgur Atalay, Fatma Kalaoglu, and Senem Kursun Bahadir. Development of textile-based transmission lines using conductive yarns and ultrasonic welding technology for e-textile applications. *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 14:1558925019856603, 2019.
- [81] Ziqi Qu, Zhechen Zhu, Yulong Liu, Mengxia Yu, and Terry Tao Ye. Parasitic capacitance modeling and measurements of conductive yarns for e-textile devices. *Nature Communications*, 14(1):2785, 2023.
- [82] ÜNER İbrahim and Banu Hatice GÜRCÜM. Applications of technical embroidery and conductive yarns in e-textile design. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL HUMANITIES SCIENCES RESEARCH*, 6(44):3376–3388, 2019.
- [83] Alenka Ojstršek, Olivija Plohl, Selestina Gorgieva, Manja Kurečič, Urška Jančič, Silvo Hribernik, and Darinka Fakin. Metallisation of textiles and protection of conductive layers: an overview of application techniques. *Sensors*, 21(10):3508, 2021.
- [84] Alenka Ojstršek, Laura Jug, and Olivija Plohl. A review of electro conductive textiles utilizing the dip-coating technique: their functionality, durability and sustainability. *Polymers*, 14(21):4713, 2022.
- [85] SangUn Kim, TranThuyNga Truong, JunHyuk Jang, and Jooyong Kim. The programmable design of large-area piezoresistive textile sensors using manufacturing by jacquard processing. *Polymers*, 15(1):78, 2022.
- [86] Paula Veske, Frederick Bossuyt, and Jan Vanfleteren. Testing for wearability and reliability of tpu lamination method in e-textiles. *Sensors*, 22(1):156, 2021.
- [87] Yong Lin, Xiaolian Chen, Qianying Lu, Jiayi Wang, Chen Ding, Fuxing Liu, Desheng Kong, Wei Yuan, Wenming Su, and Zheng Cui. Thermally laminated lighting textile for wearable displays with high durability. *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 15(4):5931–5941, 2023.
- [88] Esubalew Kasaw, Adane Haile, and Melkie Getnet. Conductive coatings of cotton fabric consisting of carbonized charcoal for e-textile. *Coatings*, 10(6):579, 2020.
- [89] Nupur Maheshwari, Marwa Abd-Ellah, and IA Goldthorpe. Transfer printing of silver nanowire conductive ink for e-textile applications. *Flexible and Printed Electronics*, 4(2):025005, 2019.

- [90] Rashedul Islam, Nipa Khair, Dewan Murshed Ahmed, and Hasan Shahariar. Fabrication of low cost and scalable carbon-based conductive ink for e-textile applications. *Materials Today Communications*, 19:32–38, 2019.
- [91] Vigyanshu Mishra and Asimina Kiourti. Electromagnetic components realized on conductive wires: A copper vs. e-thread comparison. In *2019 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and USNC-URSI Radio Science Meeting*, pages 359–360. IEEE, 2019.
- [92] Abiodun Komolafe, Bahareh Zaghari, Russel Torah, Alex S Weddell, Hamideh Khanbareh, Zois Michail Tsikriteas, Mark Vousden, Mahmoud Wagih, Ulises Tronco Jurado, Junjie Shi, et al. E-textile technology review—from materials to application. *Ieee Access*, 9:97152–97179, 2021.
- [93] Jessica Stanley, Katy Griggs, Oliver Handford, John A Hunt, Phil Kunovski, and Yang Wei. Modular e-textile platform for real-time sensing. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM International Symposium on Wearable Computers*, pages 131–135, 2022.
- [94] Mario Gonzalez, Fabrice Axisa, Mathieu Vanden Bulcke, Dominique Brosteaux, Bart Vandeveld, and Jan Vanfleteren. Design of metal interconnects for stretchable electronic circuits. *Microelectronics reliability*, 48(6):825–832, 2008.
- [95] Abiodun Komolafe, Russel Torah, Yang Wei, Helga Nunes-Matos, Menglong Li, Dorothy Hardy, Tilak Dias, Michael Tudor, and Stephen Beeby. Integrating flexible filament circuits for e-textile applications. *Advanced Materials Technologies*, 4(7):1900176, 2019.
- [96] Sung Hwan Kim, Jin-Hee Moon, Jeong Hun Kim, Sung Min Jeong, and Sang-Hoon Lee. Flexible, stretchable and implantable pdms encapsulated cable for implantable medical device. *Biomedical Engineering Letters*, 1:199–203, 2011.
- [97] AO Komolafe, RN Torah, MJ Tudor, and SP Beeby. Modelling and experimental validation of the effect of the elastic properties of fabrics on the durability of screen printed e-textiles. *Smart Materials and Structures*, 27(7):075046, 2018.
- [98] Hong-Wu Zhu, Huai-Ling Gao, Hao-Yu Zhao, Jin Ge, Bi-Cheng Hu, Jin Huang, and Shu-Hong Yu. Printable elastic silver nanowire-based conductor for washable electronic textiles. *Nano Research*, 13:2879–2884, 2020.
- [99] Ying-Chih Lai, Hong-Wei Lu, Hsing-Mei Wu, Dongguang Zhang, Jiayi Yang, Jinwoo Ma, Mohammad Shamsi, Veena Vallem, and Michael D Dickey. Elastic multifunctional liquid–metal fibers for harvesting mechanical and electromagnetic energy and as self-powered sensors. *Advanced Energy Materials*, 11(18):2100411, 2021.

- [100] Sigrid Rotzler and Martin Schneider-Ramelow. Washability of e-textiles: failure modes and influences on washing reliability. *Textiles*, 1(1):37–54, 2021.
- [101] Shahood uz Zaman, Xuyuan Tao, Cédric Cochrane, and Vladan Koncar. Launderability of conductive polymer yarns used for connections of e-textile modules: Mechanical stresses. *Fibers and Polymers*, 20:2355–2366, 2019.
- [102] Shaila Afroj, Sirui Tan, Amr M Abdelkader, Kostya S Novoselov, and Nazmul Karim. Highly conductive, scalable, and machine washable graphene-based e-textiles for multifunctional wearable electronic applications. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 30(23):2000293, 2020.
- [103] Bin Tian, Yuhui Fang, Jing Liang, Ke Zheng, Panwang Guo, Xinyu Zhang, Youfusheng Wu, Qun Liu, Zhida Huang, Changyong Cao, et al. Fully printed stretchable and multifunctional e-textiles for aesthetic wearable electronic systems. *Small*, 18(13):2107298, 2022.
- [104] Marina Sala de Medeiros, Debkalpa Goswami, Daniela Chanci, Carolina Moreno, and Ramses V Martinez. Washable, breathable, and stretchable e-textiles wirelessly powered by omniphobic silk-based coils. *Nano Energy*, 87:106155, 2021.
- [105] Jiancheng Dong, Yidong Peng, Lei Pu, Kangqi Chang, Le Li, Chao Zhang, Piming Ma, Yunpeng Huang, and Tianxi Liu. Perspiration-wicking and luminescent on-skin electronics based on ultrastretchable janus e-textiles. *Nano Letters*, 22(18):7597–7605, 2022.
- [106] Melkie Getnet Tadesse, Rodica Harpa, Yan Chen, Lichuan Wang, Vincent Nierstrasz, and Carmen Loghin. Assessing the comfort of functional fabrics for smart clothing using subjective evaluation. *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, 48(8):1310–1326, 2019.
- [107] Jaana Rantanen, Timo Vuorela, Kari Kukkonen, Outi Ryyanen, Arto Siili, and Jukka Vanhala. Improving human thermal comfort with smart clothing. In *2001 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics. e-Systems and e-Man for Cybernetics in Cyberspace (Cat. No. 01CH37236)*, volume 2, pages 795–800. IEEE, 2001.
- [108] Min Chen, Yujun Ma, Jeungeun Song, Chin-Feng Lai, and Bin Hu. Smart clothing: Connecting human with clouds and big data for sustainable health monitoring. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 21:825–845, 2016.
- [109] Prabod Munasinghe, Angela Druckman, and DGK Dissanayake. A systematic review of the life cycle inventory of clothing. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 320:128852, 2021.
- [110] S Lam Po Tang and GK Stylios. An overview of smart technologies for clothing design and engineering. *International Journal of Clothing Science and Technology*, 18(2):108–128, 2006.

- [111] Ana Paula Provin, Ana Regina de Aguiar Dutra, Marina Medeiros Machado, and Anelise Leal Vieira Cubas. New materials for clothing: Rethinking possibilities through a sustainability approach-a review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 282:124444, 2021.
- [112] Yifei Wang, Huizhi Wang, Jin Xuan, and Dennis YC Leung. Powering future body sensor network systems: A review of power sources. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 166:112410, 2020.
- [113] P Lam. The application of communication technologies in smart clothing. In *Smart Clothes and Wearable Technology*, pages 205–213. Elsevier, 2009.
- [114] Bhargav Jethwa, Milit Panchasara, Abhi Zanzarukiya, and Rutu Parekh. Realtime wireless embedded electronics for soldier security. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Computing and Communication Technologies (CONECCT)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2020.
- [115] Dionisis Kandris, Christos Nakas, Dimitrios Vomvas, and Grigorios Koulouras. Applications of wireless sensor networks: an up-to-date survey. *Applied system innovation*, 3(1):14, 2020.
- [116] Ji Guanni. Design and implementation of a high-performance and low-power programmable embedded weak signal processing platform. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Telecommunications, Optics and Computer Science (TOCS)*, pages 368–371. IEEE, 2020.
- [117] Jane McCann and David Bryson. *Smart clothes and wearable technology*. Woodhead Publishing, 2022.
- [118] Ezgi Ismar, Senem Kurşun Bahadır, Fatma Kalaoglu, and Vladan Koncar. Futuristic clothes: electronic textiles and wearable technologies. *Global Challenges*, 4(7):1900092, 2020.
- [119] Krisjanis Nesenbergs and Leo Selavo. Smart textiles for wearable sensor networks: Review and early lessons. In *2015 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA) Proceedings*, pages 402–406. IEEE, 2015.
- [120] Atis Hermanis, Krisjanis Nesenbergs, Ricards Cacurs, and Modris Greitans. Wearable posture monitoring system with biofeedback via smartphone. *Journal of Medical and Bioengineering Vol*, 2(1), 2013.
- [121] Atis Hermanis, Ricards Cacurs, Krisjanis Nesenbergs, Modris Greitans, Emil Syundyukov, and Leo Selavo. Wearable sensor grid architecture for body posture and surface detection and rehabilitation. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Information Processing in Sensor Networks*, pages 414–415, 2015.
- [122] Atis Hermanis, Ricards Cacurs, Krisjanis Nesenbergs, Modris Greitans, Emil Syundyukov, and Leo Selavo. Wearable sensor system for human biomechanics monitoring. In *EWSN*, pages 247–248, 2016.

- [123] XM Tao. *Wearable electronics and photonics*. Elsevier, 2005.
- [124] Yu Chen, Yiduo Yang, Mengjiao Li, Erdong Chen, Weilei Mu, Rosie Fisher, and Rong Yin. Wearable actuators: An overview. *Textiles*, 1(2):283–321, 2021.
- [125] H Ceren Ates, Peter Q Nguyen, Laura Gonzalez-Macia, Eden Morales-Narváez, Firat Güder, James J Collins, and Can Dincer. End-to-end design of wearable sensors. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 7(11):887–907, 2022.
- [126] Sandeep Singh Sran and Jagtar Singh Sivia. Design of a novel wearable hybrid fractal antenna for wi-fi, bluetooth, and wimax applications. *Wireless Personal Communications*, pages 1–19, 2023.
- [127] Brian P Crow, Indra Widjaja, Jeong Geun Kim, and Prescott T Sakai. Ieee 802.11 wireless local area networks. *IEEE Communications magazine*, 35(9):116–126, 1997.
- [128] BLUETOOTH SIG. Specification of the bluetooth system. <http://www.bluetooth.com/>, 2001.
- [129] Andrew Martin, Boyce S Chang, Zachariah Martin, Dipak Paramanik, Christophe Frankiewicz, Souvik Kundu, Ian D Tevis, and Martin Thuo. Heat-free fabrication of metallic interconnects for flexible/wearable devices. *Advanced Functional Materials*, 29(40):1903687, 2019.
- [130] Fardin Derogarian, Ruben Dias, Joao Canas Ferreira, Vitor M Grade Tavares, and José Machado da Silva. Using a wired body area network for locomotion data acquisition. In *Proc. 27th Conf. Design Circuits Integr. Syst. (DCIS)*, pages 1–6, 2012.
- [131] Khalid Hasan, Kamanashis Biswas, Khandakar Ahmed, Nazmus S Nafi, and Md Saiful Islam. A comprehensive review of wireless body area network. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, 143:178–198, 2019.
- [132] David Naranjo-Hernández, Amparo Callejón-Leblic, Željka Lučev Vasić, MirHojjat Seyedi, Yue-Ming Gao, et al. Past results, present trends, and future challenges in intrabody communication. *Wireless communications and mobile computing*, 2018, 2018.
- [133] Hassan Ghasemzadeh and Roozbeh Jafari. Ultra low-power signal processing in wearable monitoring systems: A tiered screening architecture with optimal bit resolution. *ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems (TECS)*, 13(1):1–23, 2013.
- [134] Srinivasa R Sridhara. Ultra-low power microcontrollers for portable, wearable, and implantable medical electronics. In *16th Asia and South Pacific Design Automation Conference (ASP-DAC 2011)*, pages 556–560. IEEE, 2011.

- [135] Dhruv Gajaria and Tosiron Adegbiya. Evaluating the performance and energy of stt-ram caches for real-world wearable workloads. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 136:231–240, 2022.
- [136] Lahir Marni, Morteza Hosseini, Jennifer Hopp, Pedram Mohseni, and Tinoosh Mohsenin. A real-time wearable fpga-based seizure detection processor using mcmc. In *2018 IEEE international symposium on circuits and systems (ISCAS)*, pages 1–4. IEEE, 2018.
- [137] Siddhartha Das, Stefan Bäuml, and Mark M Wilde. Entanglement and secret-key-agreement capacities of bipartite quantum interactions and read-only memory devices. *Physical Review A*, 101(1):012344, 2020.
- [138] EV Kostikova, SA Seliverstov, Ya A Seliverstov, and Sh S Fahmi. Measuring the speed of data exchange in memory cards using programmable logic integrated circuits. *Measurement Techniques*, 62:23–30, 2019.
- [139] Seung Soo Kim, Soo Kyeom Yong, Whyoung Kim, Sukin Kang, Hyeon Woo Park, Kyung Jean Yoon, Dong Sun Sheen, Seho Lee, and Cheol Seong Hwang. Review of semiconductor flash memory devices for material and process issues. *Advanced Materials*, page 2200659, 2022.
- [140] Qi Yang, Ao Chen, Chuan Li, Gangsheng Zou, Hongfei Li, and Chunyi Zhi. Categorizing wearable batteries: Unidirectional and omnidirectional deformable batteries. *Matter*, 4(10):3146–3160, 2021.
- [141] Siyu Qiang, Tian Carey, Adrees Arbab, Weihua Song, Chaoxia Wang, and Felice Torrisi. Wearable solid-state capacitors based on two-dimensional material all-textile heterostructures. *Nanoscale*, 11(20):9912–9919, 2019.
- [142] Atif Sardar Khan and Farid Ullah Khan. A survey of wearable energy harvesting systems. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 46(3):2277–2329, 2022.
- [143] Danmei Sun, Meixuan Chen, Symon Podilchak, Apostolos Georgiadis, Qassim S Abdullahi, Rahil Joshi, Sohail Yasin, Jean Rooney, and John Rooney. Investigating flexible textile-based coils for wireless charging wearable electronics. *Journal of industrial textiles*, 50(3):333–345, 2020.
- [144] Yubai Zhang, Ge Shi, Jiadong Qin, Sean E Lowe, Shanqing Zhang, Huijun Zhao, and Yu Lin Zhong. Recent progress of direct ink writing of electronic components for advanced wearable devices. *ACS Applied Electronic Materials*, 1(9):1718–1734, 2019.
- [145] Shanliangzi Liu, Dylan S Shah, and Rebecca Kramer-Bottiglio. Highly stretchable multilayer electronic circuits using biphasic gallium-indium. *Nature Materials*, 20(6):851–858, 2021.

- [146] Leandro Donisi, Gaetano Pagano, Giuseppe Cesarelli, Armando Coccia, Federica Amitrano, and Giovanni D’Addio. Benchmarking between two wearable inertial systems for gait analysis based on a different sensor placement using several statistical approaches. *Measurement*, 173:108642, 2021.
- [147] Kai Kunze and Paul Lukowicz. Sensor placement variations in wearable activity recognition. *IEEE Pervasive Computing*, 13(4):32–41, 2014.
- [148] Dawei Jiang, Guoquan Shi, et al. Research on data security and privacy protection of wearable equipment in healthcare. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2021, 2021.
- [149] Arup Barua, Md Abdullah Al Alamin, Md Shohrab Hossain, and Ekram Hossain. Security and privacy threats for bluetooth low energy in iot and wearable devices: A comprehensive survey. *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 3:251–281, 2022.
- [150] Raquel Benbunan-Fich. User satisfaction with wearables. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*, 12(1):1–27, 2020.
- [151] Jun Huang, Yide Zhou, Zhaolong Ning, and Hamid Gharavi. Wireless power transfer and energy harvesting: Current status and future prospects. *IEEE wireless communications*, 26(4):163–169, 2019.
- [152] Jiamin Li, Yilong Dong, Jeong Hoan Park, Longyang Lin, Tao Tang, and Jerald Yoo. Body-area powering with human body-coupled power transmission and energy harvesting ics. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Circuits and Systems*, 14(6):1263–1273, 2020.
- [153] Shovan Maity, Mayukh Nath, Gargi Bhattacharya, Baibhab Chatterjee, and Shreyas Sen. On the safety of human body communication. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 67(12):3392–3402, 2020.
- [154] Qingling Liu, Kefa G Mkongwa, and Chaozhu Zhang. Performance issues in wireless body area networks for the healthcare application: a survey and future prospects. *SN Applied Sciences*, 3:1–19, 2021.
- [155] Emy Mariam George and Lillykutty Jacob. Interference mitigation for coexisting wireless body area networks: Distributed learning solutions. *IEEE Access*, 8:24209–24218, 2020.
- [156] Armands Ancans, Juris Ormanis, Ricards Cacurs, Modris Greitans, Elise Saoutieff, Adrien Faucorr, and Sebastien Boisseau. Bluetooth low energy throughput in densely deployed radio environment. In *2019 23rd International Conference Electronics*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2019.
- [157] Kristtopher Coelho, Danilo Damião, Guevara Noubir, Alex Borges, Michele Nogueira, and José Nacif. Cryptographic algorithms in wearable communications: An empirical analysis. *IEEE Communications Letters*, 23(11):1931–1934, 2019.

- [158] Bernhards Blumbergs, Eriks Dobelis, Peteris Paikens, Krisjanis Nesenbergs, Kirils Solovjovs, and Artis Rusins. Wearsec: Towards automated security evaluation of wireless wearable devices. In *Nordic Conference on Secure IT Systems*, pages 311–325. Springer, 2022.
- [159] Liezel Cilliers. Wearable devices in healthcare: Privacy and information security issues. *Health information management journal*, 49(2-3):150–156, 2020.
- [160] Kenneth R Foster and John Torous. The opportunity and obstacles for smartwatches and wearable sensors. *IEEE pulse*, 10(1):22–25, 2019.
- [161] Eric Elenko, Austin Speier, and Daphne Zohar. A regulatory framework emerges for digital medicine. *Nature biotechnology*, 33(7):697–702, 2015.
- [162] Juris Ormanis and Krisjanis Nesenbergs. Human skin as data transmission medium for improved privacy and usability in wearable electronics. In *2018 IEEE International Symposium on Medical Measurements and Applications (MeMeA)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2018.
- [163] Leslie Mertz. E-textiles for health monitoring: off to a slow start, but coming soon. *IEEE pulse*, 11(3):20–24, 2020.
- [164] Paula Veske, Frederick Bossuyt, Filip Thielemans, and Jan Vanfleteren. Measuring the flex life of conductive yarns in narrow fabric. *Micromachines*, 14(4):781, 2023.
- [165] Harneet Arora, Robert Simon Sherratt, Balazs Janko, and William Harwin. Experimental validation of the recovery effect in batteries for wearable sensors and healthcare devices discovering the existence of hidden time constants. *The Journal of Engineering*, 2017(10):548–556, 2017.
- [166] James J Licari. Coating materials for electronic applications: polymers, processing, reliability, testing. 2003.
- [167] Jeffrey ChangBing Lee, Weifeng Liu, ChangHo Lo, and Cheng-Chih Chen. Laundering reliability of electrically conductive fabrics for e-textile applications. In *2019 IEEE 69th electronic components and technology conference (ECTC)*, pages 1826–1832. IEEE, 2019.
- [168] Alex Z Kattamis, Patrick F Murphy, Matthew Pooley, and Alexander Soane. Water infiltration in common residential and commercial power cables introduced by capillary action. In *2020 IEEE Symposium on Product Compliance Engineering-(SPCE Portland)*, pages 1–3. IEEE, 2020.
- [169] Kishor Joshi and Ruchi Mehrotra. Internet of medical things—state-of-the-art. *Advanced Healthcare Systems: Empowering Physicians with IoT-Enabled Technologies*, pages 1–20, 2022.
- [170] Lucy Dunne. Smart clothing in practice: Key design barriers to commercialization. *Fashion Practice*, 2(1):41–65, 2010.

- [171] Rajkishore Nayak and Rajiv Padhye. *Garment manufacturing technology*. Elsevier, 2015.
- [172] Sungmee Park and Sundaresan Jayaraman. Smart textiles: Wearable electronic systems. *MRS bulletin*, 28(8):585–591, 2003.
- [173] Ikra Iftekhar Shuvo, Justine Decaens, Dominic Lachapelle, and P Dolez. *Smart textiles testing: A roadmap to standardized test methods for safety and quality-control*. IntechOpen London, UK, 2021.
- [174] Youngjin Chae and Juan Hinestroza. Building circular economy for smart textiles, smart clothing, and future wearables. *Materials Circular Economy*, 2(1):2, 2020.
- [175] I Gehrke, V Tenner, V Lutz, D Schmelzeisen, and T Gries. Production technologies for electronic textiles. *Smart Textiles Production: Overview of Materials, Sensor and Production Technologies for Industrial Smart Textiles*, page 31, 2019.
- [176] Matteo Stoppa and Alessandro Chiolerio. Wearable electronics and smart textiles: A critical review. *sensors*, 14(7):11957–11992, 2014.
- [177] Chandramohan Gopalsamy, Sungmee Park, Rangaswamy Rajamanickam, and Sundaresan Jayaraman. The wearable motherboardTM: The first generation of adaptive and responsive textile structures (arts) for medical applications. *Virtual Reality*, 4:152–168, 1999.
- [178] Sungmee Park, Kenneth Mackenzie, and Sundaresan Jayaraman. The wearable motherboard: A framework for personalized mobile information processing (pmip). In *proceedings of the 39th annual design automation conference*, pages 170–174, 2002.
- [179] Ivo Locher. *Technologies for system-on-textile integration*. PhD thesis, ETH Zurich, 2006.
- [180] Marc Martínez-Estrada, Bahareh Moradi, Raúl Fernández-García, and Ignacio Gil. Impact of conductive yarns on an embroidery textile moisture sensor. *Sensors*, 19(5):1004, 2019.
- [181] Sungyong Shin, Baesun Kim, Yong Ki Son, Ji Eun Kim, and Il-Yeon Cho. A flexible textile wristwatch using transfer printed textile circuit technique. In *2012 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, pages 21–22. IEEE, 2012.
- [182] Yuan Xiao, Qian Li, Chengkun Zhang, Wei Zhang, Weibo Yun, and Leipeng Yang. Fabrication of silver electrical circuits on textile substrates by reactive inkjet printing. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 22(11):11056–11064, 2022.

- [183] Nils Grimmelsmann, Yasmin Martens, Patricia Schäl, Hubert Meissner, and Andrea Ehrmann. Mechanical and electrical contacting of electronic components on textiles by 3d printing. *Procedia Technology*, 26:66–71, 2016.
- [184] Laura Devendorf and Chad Di Lauro. Adapting double weaving and yarn plying techniques for smart textiles applications. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*, pages 77–85, 2019.
- [185] Nicolas P Fromme, Yifan Li, Martin Camenzind, Claudio Toncelli, and René M Rossi. Metal-textile laser welding for wearable sensors applications. *Advanced Electronic Materials*, 7(4):2001238, 2021.
- [186] Jung-Sim Roh. All-fabric interconnection and one-stop production process for electronic textile sensors. *Textile Research Journal*, 87(12):1445–1456, 2017.
- [187] Ivan Poupyrev, Nan-Wei Gong, Shiho Fukuhara, Mustafa Emre Karagozler, Carsten Schwesig, and Karen E Robinson. Project jacquard: interactive digital textiles at scale. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 4216–4227, 2016.
- [188] Pantas, Tig Sutardja Center for Entrepreneurship, and Alex Hanuska. *Smart clothing market analysis*. Sutardja Center for Entrepreneurship, 2022.
- [189] Grand View Research. Revenue of the apparel market worldwide from 2014 to 2027. Statista Inc., New York, United States, 2023.
- [190] Andrew Godley. The development of the clothing industry: technology and fashion, 1997.
- [191] Ylva Fernaeus, Martin Jonsson, and Jakob Tholander. Revisiting the jacquard loom: threads of history and current patterns in hci. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1593–1602, 2012.
- [192] Craig Karl. The state of fashion 2017. Technical report, McKinsey Global Institute, 2017.
- [193] Giovanna Capponi, Arianna Martinelli, and Alessandro Nuvolari. Breakthrough innovations and where to find them. *Research Policy*, 51(1):104376, 2022.
- [194] Shadia Moazzem, Enda Crossin, Fugen Daver, and Lijing Wang. Environmental impact of apparel supply chain and textile products. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, pages 1–19, 2021.

- [195] Muhammad Haseeb, Ilham Haouas, Mohammad Nasih, Leonardus WW Mihardjo, and Kittisak Jermsittiparsert. Asymmetric impact of textile and clothing manufacturing on carbon-dioxide emissions: Evidence from top asian economies. *Energy*, 196:117094, 2020.
- [196] Qing Li, Zhebin Xue, Yuhan Wu, and Xianyi Zeng. The status quo and prospect of sustainable development of smart clothing. *Sustainability*, 14(2):990, 2022.
- [197] P Bosowski, M Hoerr, V Mecnika, T Gries, and S Jockenhövel. Design and manufacture of textile-based sensors. In *Electronic Textiles*, pages 75–107. Elsevier, 2015.
- [198] Augustinus J Berkhout, Dap Hartmann, Patrick Van Der Duin, and Roland Ortt. Innovating the innovation process. *International journal of technology management*, 34(3-4):390–404, 2006.
- [199] Donald W Mitchell and Carol Bruckner Coles. Establishing a continuing business model innovation process. *Journal of business strategy*, 25(3):39–49, 2004.
- [200] LV Navolska. Study of peculiarities of form and style in the design of menswear in the xx century. *Art and Design*, 2023.
- [201] Krisjanis Nesenbergs. Architecture of smart clothing for standardized wearable sensor systems. *IEEE Instrumentation & Measurement Magazine*, 19(5):36–64, 2016.
- [202] Krisjanis Nesenbergs. Equilateral monogonal tessellation of arbitrary polygons-a recursive algorithm. *Malaysian Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 13:51–64, 2019.